

SECTION OF HUMANITIES AND PHILOLOGY

AI AND BLOCKCHAIN AS A MEANS OF UPDATING TEXTBOOKS FOR ESD

Dziatkovskii A.,

PhD in Education, (Information Technologies)

Dzyatkovskaya E.

Prof., Doctor of Biological Science

Abstract

The features of education for sustainable development compared to subject-based learning are considered. It is concluded that subject reductionism must be overcome in order for students to understand global issues and to be able to look at school subjects from the perspective of the Sustainable Development Goals. A digital framework for embedding education for sustainable development in school subject textbooks is proposed. The role of AI and blockchain in updating the content of school education is justified to improve the quality of subject learning and to ensure that education for sustainable development has an institutional-wide status.

Keywords: education for sustainable development, textbooks, artificial intelligent, blockchain.

Many teachers continue to teach "from the textbook". School textbooks are authoritative sources of knowledge and transmission of social values for teachers and students. The Global Education Monitoring Report 'Textbooks Paving the Way for Sustainable Development' (2017) focused on the relevance of textbook renewal by embedding education for sustainable development [1]. The Club of Rome's Jubilee Report "COME ON!", produced in the same year, also devoted a lot of attention to textbooks. The verdict was that textbooks reflect the state of science of the last century [2]. Governments should review textbook content in line with the core values of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development [3]. National guidelines for textbook authors to update textbooks are needed. Attention should also be paid to those responsible for illustrations in textbooks, as many of them, as well as textbook texts, contain ideas of a consumer society that are opposed to the values of sustainable development. Integrating Education for Sustainable Development into textbook content is the essence of textbook renewal, enhancing quality and accessibility for all (SDG 4). Integrating ESD into core subjects is one of the most effective and efficient ways of addressing SDG Target 4.7. Textbooks are mandatory texts for students. Pupils spend most of their time with textbooks. The content of textbooks is reflected in quizzes and examinations. Integration of education for sustainable development into textbook content enables students to form values of sustainable development, environmental responsibility and principles of environmentally sound behavior.

Orienting the textbook towards ESD gives the subject a new purpose, in addition to the subject objective. Learning with a dual purpose, although it introduces an increase in the volume of the textbook, provides an opportunity to improve the quality of the learning outcomes of the subject. ESD is a way of studying any object from the perspective of its relation to environmental, social and economic processes. ESD integrates knowledge about local and global issues. ESD provides an understanding of the links between the past, present and future (4). ESD is about deepening our understanding of subject knowledge so we can understand the

world around us and how to engage with it constructively. ESD is a means of human socialisation in the world, a readiness to act independently on sustainable development issues [5]. ESD makes academic knowledge concrete, understandable and meaningful. ESD introduces principles of behaviour in the surrounding world to enhance its human dimension, forms a picture of the world in its unity, orientates towards social-humanistic ideas of sustainable development - environmental quality, respect for cultural and natural diversity, biosphere-compatible lifestyles [6]. The content of the subject is enriched with global competence - "the ability to analyse global and intercultural issues critically and from different perspectives". According to Pisa developments, global competence is an important tool for reflecting on subject knowledge, e.g. on climate, poverty, migration, environmental issues. Students learn how to collect data from different sources, using different tools; to critically assess their quality and extract useful information; and to generate knowledge to solve problems. They learn to recognise the results of human intervention in the environment; to analyse emerging risks, to predict future options taking into account the factor of uncertainty [7].

The inclusion of ESD in textbooks strengthens the interdisciplinary approach in education and contributes to overcoming subject reductionism. Textbooks are beginning to include interdisciplinary topics ('global climate change', 'health-safety-human well-being', 'global environmental change', etc.) that are not possible from a subject perspective.

This interdisciplinarity is essential in an increasingly global society, where "everything is connected to everything" is becoming a truism from an aphorism. ESD draws students' attention to the broad social, environmental, economic and political issues of the real 'unrefined' world, and increases their preparedness to live in and solve problems in a rapidly changing world [8].

What should be included in the content of textbooks? The conceptual apparatus of ESD; scientific knowledge about and for sustainable development; the bundles of scientific knowledge needed to understand sustainable development, and, of course, the problematics of values and attitudes: Who is in charge on Earth?

The spiritual versus the material? The individual versus the social? Domination or cooperation? Nature management or self-management? [9]

What scientific knowledge underlies the concept of sustainable development? The material unity of the world, the law of physical and chemical unity of living matter on the planet, conservation laws, basics of thermodynamics, systems theory, laws of self-organising systems, basics of homeostatics, laws of ecology (rule of constancy of number of species in the biosphere, one percent rule, Liebig's law of minimum) and others [10].

Integrating ESD into textbooks is a complex, prototype-free, multi-faceted, global task which covers textbooks for all subjects, all types of educational institutions and national education systems. Artificial intelligence technologies can contribute to this task [11]. The potential of artificial intelligence in education is great. Appropriate and effective use of AI can reconcile the two objectives of a textbook (the subject itself and ESD); integrate knowledge about local and global issues; present subject knowledge through an interdisciplinary lens; and bring textbook content into the real world [9]. AI helps textbook developers to expand the information base, to incorporate information from different sources and to make connections between different data.

AI helps textbook developers expand the information base, incorporate information from different sources and make connections between different data on large spatial and temporal scales. Artificial intelligence can help reconcile the two objectives of a textbook - subject matter and for sustainable development. AI helps with the tasks of visualising complex phenomena that cannot be observed in normal life; making connections between local and global issues; textbook content and the real world; adjusting course content in real time, etc. [11,12]. Artificial intelligence will make it possible to identify links between social, economic and natural processes in specific situations, using extensive data. Such links provide a starting point for understanding local sustainability issues and responsible decision-making.

AI can also help in the assessment phase of education outcomes. Traditional indicators and procedures are ill-suited to assessing learning outcomes 'with two objectives', which involve a combination of subject, meta-subject and personal criteria. AI is a means of developing individual trajectories that take into account the socio-cultural learning environment, the individual characteristics of the student, the specificity of current environmental problems and the opportunity to take part in solving them as much as possible.

The knowledge base in many subject areas, especially in science and technology, is changing and expanding rapidly. Therefore, the prospects for the use of artificial intelligence are linked to its alliance with blockchain. Blockchain is a technology for creating and storing records that uses a distributed database to improve textbooks for learning subjects that implement ESD. For textbook creators and users, blockchain is an opportunity to organize information, build interdisciplinary content, and make information flows transparent

for updating learning materials on sustainable development and its theory and practice. The alliance of artificial intelligence and blockchain is an opportunity to use large volumes of data, analyse them, improve the relevance and accuracy of existing information and quickly make changes to it, preserving the history of these changes, building individual learning trajectories, implementing the principle of its accessibility. AI combined with blockchain allows improving the quality of subject education and ensuring the "vertical" integrity of its ESD components, consistency and continuity of their inclusion in the subject content to ensure the integrity of education for sustainable development. Moreover, the described digital technologies will be the basis for the implementation of a whole-institutional approach to the implementation of ESD in an educational organization, including different forms and types of students' activities, different structures of the educational organization, even different branches, which may be located in different countries. AI with blockchain is a better management in all parts of the life of an educational organization in close connection with the surrounding educational space, creating an educational ecosystem for sustainable development.

In contrast to AI, traditional forms of assessment are ill-suited to assessing learning outcomes for sustainable development: general cultural skills, communication skills, morale, ability to interact, collaborate and work effectively in teams. AI and blockchain make it possible to assess a child's learning not only in terms of their grades but also in terms of their personal qualities. AI makes it possible to make students co-present environmental predictions, develop individual trajectories for inclusion in sustainable community development programmes and adjust course content in real time [12]. AI is indispensable for visualizing the relationships between global and local, past-present and future problems, their natural - social and economic aspects. Such linkages provide a starting point for understanding local and global sustainability issues. The knowledge base in many subject areas, especially in science and technology, is changing and expanding rapidly. A textbook can become obsolete as soon as it is approved. AI makes it possible to work with big data and update it quickly. The use of AI in alliance with blockchain is promising. The alliance of artificial intelligence and blockchain is the ability to use large amounts of data, analyse it, improve the relevance and accuracy of existing information and quickly make changes to it, preserving the history of those changes. Blockchain is a technology for creating and storing records that uses a distributed database to improve textbooks for learning subjects that implement ESD. Blockchain is a means of systematizing information, optimizing forms of presentation, constructing interdisciplinary content, and processing the results of 'two goals' in their interconnectedness [11].

In a rapidly changing world, there is an urgent need to update textbook content. The point of this renewal is to bring them into line with ideas of sustainable development. Despite the outward simplicity of the solution, we are talking about a fundamental overhaul

of the entire education system. Textbooks are an important tool for this process. The prospects for their renewal seem to lie in the use of artificial intelligence in tandem with blockchain technology.

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